

A 6G Vision for Intelligent Emergency Communication: Unified 3D Networking and Ambient IoT

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Abstract—The emergence of 6G networks paves the way for a new era of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-empowered integration of Internet of Things (IoT), autonomous mobile robots (AMRs) and extended reality (XR). This will revolutionise the ways users (e.g., humans, robots) interact with each other and their surroundings expanding their awareness beyond immediate boundaries. Driven by demand for more effective emergency response fuelled by adverse and increasing impacts of climate change, in this paper, we conceptually explore an architectural framework for intelligent emergency response services in 6G networks. The proposed architecture bridges an evolution of supporting technologies in 5G with future intelligent emergency response service requirements. We identify integration of 3D networking (3DN) and ambient IoT (A-IoT), empowered by native AI, network sensing and localisation, as key technologies for the proposed framework. We conclude the paper with discussion on current technology gaps and recommendations that would lead towards future 6G intelligent emergency response.

Index Terms—3D networking, 5G/6G, aerial-assisted architecture, ambient IoT, wireless emergency communications

I. INTRODUCTION

Disaster events caused by natural hazards impact populations globally, resulting in loss of life and significant economic consequences. Climate change exacerbates this problem, leading to more frequent extreme weather events [1]. The lack of advanced network infrastructure in remote areas leaves unconnected populations vulnerable to these disasters, with limited access to emergency response (ER) services. First responders rely heavily on high-rate connectivity, image/video transmission, ambient sensing, location tracking, and data analytics for effective ER operations [2], [3]. ER missions in remote and dangerous environments utilize wireless connectivity, drones, autonomous mobile robots (AMRs), ambient sensors, and staff equipped with wearable sensors and XR/AR devices, relying on data for timely and accurate hazard prediction, decision-making, and response [4], [5]. Multi-modal sensing and communications enhance human crew perception, enabling interaction with uncrewed ground or aerial vehicles (UGV/UAV) and ambient sensors, driving the need for the extreme wireless connectivity envisioned in 6G networks [6].

This paper presents a conceptual vision for intelligent emergency response services in 6G, leveraging technological

enablers expected from 3GPP 6G evolution, including integration of non-3GPP technologies (Fig. 1). The vision integrates advanced user equipment (UE) platforms (e.g., XR/AR devices and AMRs) within future 6G radio access networks (RAN) across two wireless domains: 3D wireless networking (3DN) [7] and ambient IoT (A-IoT) networks [8]. 3DN, supported by UAV-mounted base stations (BS) [7] and the integration of Terrestrial Network (TN) with non-terrestrial (NTN) domains [9], is crucial for resilient high-throughput connectivity of advanced UEs. Efficient A-IoT connectivity via direct and multi-hop device-to-device (D2D) links is essential for advanced UEs to interact with surrounding ambient sensors. Beyond connectivity, 6G will integrate sensing and communications (ISAC), enabling RF sensing capabilities of RAN nodes [11]. Efficient compression, transmission, and semantic processing of multi-modal data sources in 6G will rely on the native integration of machine learning (ML) and AI in beyond 5G [12], capable of closing time-critical control loops. Flexible deployment and life-cycle management of multi-modal AI (MM-AI) models across edge-cloud continuum compute resources will be critical for future 6G ER services.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. Section II reviews how 5G impacted ER service evolution. Section III explores technologies relevant to the proposed vision. Section IV presents motivating use case examples for 6G ER. Section V outlines our conceptual architectural framework for intelligent ER services in 6G. Finally, Section VI addresses technical gaps and challenges, concluding with recommendations.

II. EMERGENCY RESPONSE SERVICES IN 5G

The evolution of ER services over 5G networks received increased interest due to possible substantial improvements over previous generations [3]. With data rates much higher than 4G, 5G allows real-time transmission of high-definition videos crucial for situational awareness [13]. 5G's ultra low latency ensures near-instantaneous communication critical for time-sensitive ER services [14]. 5G improves connectivity and coverage through network slicing and NTN integration. Network slicing allows the creation of dedicated virtual networks for ER services, ensuring that public safety communications remain uninterrupted even during peak usage times [15]. The

Fig. 1. Key 6G Technologies for Intelligent Emergency Response.

deployment of 3DN including NTN in 5G for ER service is a growing area [7], [9]. NTN provides communication infrastructure that can operate efficiently in challenging environments such as disaster zones, where terrestrial networks may be compromised or unavailable [4].

5G supports advanced IoT applications and provides a platform for real-time data for AI/ML-based analysis and improving decision-making. Application examples are AR and virtual reality (VR) technologies for training emergency responders, as well as offering immersive simulations of emergency scenarios [17] and in field deployments. The ability to process and analyse large volumes of data in real-time aids in predictive analytics, early warning systems, and dynamic resource allocation during emergencies. AI-driven systems can analyse data from multi-modal sources to predict incidents, optimise response strategies, and automate routine tasks, allowing human responders to focus on critical activities [3]. 5G experimentation facilities for public safety play a critical role in testing and validating new ER networking technologies and applications under realistic circumstances. These facilities support hands-on experiments with virtualised and cloud-native 5G architectures, deployment options, and performance tests, ensuring that 5G can meet the stringent requirements of public safety operations [14], [16].

III. EVOLUTION AND CONVERGENCE OF ENABLING TECHNOLOGIES IN 6G

In this section, we discuss the enabling technologies that serve as the driving force for future 6G public safety services.

A. Resilient Networks: 3D Networking Meets Ambient IoT

Evolution of RAN through 4G and 5G made its connectivity landscape increasingly more complex. Indeed, from D2D and cellular vehicle-to-everything (C-V2X) connectivity, integrated access and backhaul nodes [10], extension of RAN to NTN nodes [9], and integration with non-3GPP technologies, 5G-to-6G RAN transition evolves to a complex multi-connected mesh network. In the context of ER services, central to this evolution are highly capable UE platforms (XR/AR headsets,

drones, AMRs, etc) whose resilient operation at any location calls for 3D multi-connectivity built across TN/NTN segment and 3GPP/non-3GPP technologies (Fig. 1). Advanced UE platforms should connect directly to surrounding ambient and on-body sensors through emerging A-IoT [8]. From the perspective of advanced 6G UE platform, we can differentiate between: i) *3DN domain* and ii) *A-IoT domain*. The former builds resilient 3D mesh network suitable for disaster scenarios where the infrastructure is damaged or non-existent. The latter expands UE reach to nearby sensors extensible to more complex tree topology via emerging sidelink relaying [18].

B. Networked Sensing and Positioning in 6G

Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) aims to enhance 6G network capability by providing wireless RF sensing services. While ISAC integration in 3GPP is at an early phase, the Wi-Fi 802.11bf extension already introduces the exposure of channel state information to third-party processes. ISAC introduces a new sensing modality, which can be utilised alongside visual, audio and haptic, for ambient understanding and expanded multi-modal perception and cognition.

Wireless positioning has been developed independently across various technologies, focusing on the propagation aspects of wireless signals, such as received signal strength, propagation time, carrier phase (CP), and direction of arrival. In 3GPP standardisation Rel-16 and Rel-17, positioning methods can be classified as Radio Access Technology (RAT)-dependent (based on cellular interface only) and RAT-independent methods (i.e., exploiting other localisation inputs and wireless interfaces). These methods can be further categorised as either UE-assisted (in which the network and external application obtain the position in order to track the UE) or UE-based (in which the UE computes its own position for the purpose of navigation) [20]. Further advancements, e.g. in 3GPP Rel-18, include CP-based positioning as a complementary method for time- and angular-based 5G positioning aiming to achieve indoor cm-level accuracy [22].

Enhanced location extraction can be achieved when the system simultaneously leverages multiple data modalities like

video, voice, or RF sensing data. The integration of MM-AI for jointly learned representations from different data types could serve as the foundation for integrating diverse positioning modalities. In cases where users cannot rely on any other preexisting positioning infrastructure (rendered inoperable in a disaster because, e.g., power lines are disrupted) or surrounding sensing system (e.g., the positioning estimation of inertial plus magnetometer deployed systems might be impaired because the computation of the orientation could be affected by strong electromagnetic interferences) [27], wearable portable devices carried by field users, could provide accurate positioning services either indoors or outdoors. Such devices could integrate a GNSS receiver, a visual-inertial odometry device (including a stereo fisheye camera and the required algorithms to provide positioning), a communications interface and a processing system hosting all related computation.

C. Extreme UE: From XR/AR headsets to A-IoT Sensors

With the evolution of 5G into 5G-Advanced [8] beginning with NR Release 18, notable improvements are being implemented to enhance support for XR applications. These enhancements include edge computing improvements that bring application servers closer to users, essential for meeting the ultra-low latency requirements of XR. Key advancements include increased XR application awareness for more efficient scheduling and resource management, dedicated power-saving optimisations for XR devices, and enhanced MIMO and beamforming capabilities for improved uplink throughput and environmental sensing. Mobility and cell management are also being refined to reduce service interruption times during handovers, crucial for maintaining seamless XR experiences.

At the opposite end of UE complexity spectrum, A-IoT sensors can enhance situational awareness and enable more effective disaster response. These devices can collect and transmit data about environmental conditions, infrastructure damage, and the location of individuals in need of assistance. Along with other multi-modal data sources, A-IoT will not only feed the data lakes for MM-AI services, but provide real-time data to be visualised on XR platforms, as well as backend visualisation services. A-IoT also provides proper background to integrate alternative IoT network technologies following standards under development for smooth interaction of 6G with other networks based on LoRa, BLE or Wi-Fi [24].

IV. INTELLIGENT EMERGENCY RESPONSE USE CASES

Consider an emergency response scenario where a team of humans and uncrewed ground or aerial vehicles collaborates. The search and rescue team member acknowledges immediate surroundings based on ambient conditions (noise, visibility). However, this information is limited, lacks coordination among team members, and fails to utilise available environmental data. To enhance their capabilities, humans may use devices like AR/XR glasses or helmets with stereo cameras for augmented reality experiences and context recognition. In situations where digital maps are inaccurate due to disasters, updates from deployed uncrewed vehicles equipped with lidars

and cameras can be crucial. They can employ haptic interfaces to control robots remotely using gestures, communicate with IoT sensors, and leverage on-body sensors for relevant data. Accurate positioning within known or unknown environments and relative positioning to other entities or incident locations are essential for heightened situational awareness. By combining visual and RF sensing, they can achieve see-through-walls perception. Processing multi-modal data on human wearables or robots, learning from this data, exchanging learned outcomes, and cooperating in the learning process with team members provide a unified representation for effective shared perception. Augmented perception enhances situational awareness and decision-making in critical missions.

Considering the above motivation example, in Table I we derive three phases of emergency use cases (UC) for indoor and outdoor scenarios defined below to motivate a new 6G intelligent emergency response framework.

Wildfire Operations: This UC enhances communication, services, and capabilities for field teams in wildfire scenarios, boosting operational capacity, safety, and situational awareness. It employs a situational awareness platform supporting various emergency services by facilitating seamless data transmission for informed decision-making. Utilising 5G, the platform prioritises PPDR-related traffic and integrates edge functionalities, slicing, and QoS mechanisms. It features UAV and AMR management solutions with advanced camera, lidar, and AR/VR applications. However, services may degrade in areas with communication or computational resource challenges. Main technology enablers to support such UCs are a) Situational awareness platforms real-time data aggregation, b) A-IoT modules with multi-modal sensors in buildings to run predictive AI algorithms to alert disasters, c) ISAC to enhance sensing capabilities for detection and classification of the objects in an unstructured scenario and in absence of cameras, d) 3DNs deployed to address network unavailability.

Damage Assessment and Survival Detection in Buildings: First responders like firefighters and SAR units in indoor settings demand uninterrupted, QoS-aware communications for teams and autonomous vehicles to be able to assess damage to human-made structures and detect survivors trapped under debris post-disasters like earthquakes. By leveraging data streams from IoT technology with multi-modal sensing in 6G and AI models, emergency communication platform can provide accurate information on the position and status of affected entities indoors. The solution integrates existing wireless infrastructure, such as 5G and Wi-Fi, with UAV nodes and IoT sensors for enhanced functionality.

V. AN ARCHITECTURAL FRAMEWORK FOR INTELLIGENT EMERGENCY RESPONSE SERVICES IN 6G

In this section, we define the conceptual architecture of intelligent ER services in 6G. The proposed architecture, presented in Fig. 2, does not explicit details of different modules, assuming that they follow 3GPP-defined 6G evolution. The proposed architecture consists of 3DN domain and A-IoT domain along with native AI/ML support for RAN optimisation

TABLE I
USE CASE SCENARIO: PRE/DURING/POST-DISASTER RESPONSE TECHNOLOGY ENABLERS

Operation stage	Field Operations (wildfire/earthquake)	Emergency Access to Buildings
Pre-emergency	a) 5G devices for real-time video and data transmission; b) IoT sensor hubs for geolocation, vital signs, and environmental sensors; c) AR goggles for immersive guidance and real-time alerts; d) UAVs and fixed cameras for surveillance e) AR-based piloting applications for UAV pilots; f) Local command and control centres connecting to NTN networks; g) Creation of 5G/Wi-Fi6 connections for operation units and equipment; h) Situational awareness platform integrated with a 3DN.	a) Massive IoT services, such as 3GPP NB-IoT or LoRa; b) UAVs (Mobile base station) equipped with 3GPP-compliant NB-IoT base stations; c) Array processing for accurate location estimation; d) NB-IoT devices and sensors RF, thermal, and voice recognition modules inside and outside critical buildings; e) Computational power for RF-based motion detection, body temperature measurement, and human voice detection; f) Activation of battery power upon receiving a wake-up signal from the base station; g) RF Energy Harvesting for Extending the Battery Life of NB-IoT Devices.
During emergency	a) UAVs for connectivity and surveillance; b) ISAC for object detection and classification in an unstructured scenario and in absence of cameras; c) 3DNs for network availability. d) UAV-BS for enhanced connectivity. e) TN/NTN convergence for improved connectivity and resilience. f) UAV-based IoT gateways and energy-optimized IoT devices for real-time data. g) Enhanced positioning with 5G, Wi-Fi, BLE, and GNSS. h) AR goggles and AMRs for map-building and SAR. i) Real-time data processing and decision support in remote command centers.	a) UAV-based BS for data collection from NB-IoT/LoRa modules with multi-modal sensors. b) Multi-modal RF/non-RF sensors for detecting survivors under debris. c) Analysis of motion/vocal/thermal variations for survivor detection. d) AI/ML-based management for TNs and UAV networks. e) Uninterrupted 3D network connectivity using 5G, UAVs, and short-range IoT devices. f) Real-time data exchange for situational awareness and decision-making. g) AR/XR platforms, stereo-vision helmets, and A-IoT sensors for accurate positioning and status updates.
Post-emergency	a) Data analysis and evaluation for post-disaster activities; b) Use of collected data to enhance preparation for future disaster and response strategies; c) 3D Model Reconstruction from Field Data for VR-Enabled Mission Planning; d) Integration of AR and VR technologies to train emergency responders for future incidents.	a) Thermal, sound, and RF sensors for gathering data from the environment; b) Terrestrial, portable, and aerial base stations; c) AI/ML approaches for intelligent network traffic management; d) Embedded AI-RAN applications for near-real-time and non-real-time processing; e) Data Processing in Mobile Operator Networks and Data Centers.

(AI-RAN) and multi-modal sensing and inference (MM-AI) as a basis for emergency response applications for localisation, perception, decision-making and data visualisation.

Advanced UE platforms: Central to the future 6G vision of intelligent emergency response are advanced connected UE platforms that include high-end devices such as AR/XR headsets or advanced autonomous platforms (UAVs, robots, or similar equipment) [5]. Their evolution from standard cellular networks UEs to more capable RAN nodes is at the core of our vision. Such UEs are bridge between 3DN and A-IoT domains, facilitating further integration of TN/NTN domains as well as 3GPP and non-3GPP technologies.

Resilient 3DN/A-IoT Communications: Advanced UEs connects to the network infrastructure through 3DN technology evolution providing resilient multi-access connectivity via multiple available wireless networks, both terrestrial (TN) and non-terrestrial (NTN) network, to edge/core network resources [7], [9]. They also connect to each other via next generation sidelink D2D/C-V2X interfaces. In addition to 3DN connectivity, UEs directly connect to surrounding A-IoT devices (A-IoT domain) through evolution of low-rate sidelink communications. A-IoT devices are designed to be energy efficient, relying on energy harvesting sources and wireless power transfer, to achieve near zero-energy operation [8], [18].

ISAC-Enabled Physical Layer: ISAC facilitates network sensing along with traditional communication services. 6G ISAC-enabled interfaces will provide novel modality for target detection, localisation and tracking [28] that can be used in stand-alone or in combination with other sensing modalities.

Native ML/AI Support: Native network support for ML/AI is fundamental for future emergency response services, firstly,

to provide communication resilience across both 3DN and A-IoT domains, and secondly, to provide support for seamless multi-modal communication and sensing based applications.

To achieve optimal operation under varying and unknown environment conditions, multi-hop topologies and channel variations, embedded AI-RAN support layer for various connectivity functions as part of the future 6G RAN is essential [12]. The proposed AI-RAN support may contain different AI models trained to facilitate efficient radio interface selection, band selection, beam management, thus achieving maximum available throughput and sensing efficiency from the available resources. It will support energy management AI models optimising energy, communication and sensing trade off.

Efficient management of ML/AI models for processing multi-modal content is essential for various emergency response applications. MM-AI layer is responsible for training, deployment and life-cycle management of MM-AI models, including distributed split or federated learning deployments. MM-AI layer will offer support for critical system applications such as multi-modal and multi-technology localisation and mapping, decision-making and visualisation (either on XR/AR-based UEs or at backend cloud facilities).

Extended Awareness Services: Collection and exchange of multi-modal streams (visual, RF, lidar, point clouds, audio, haptic) and A-IoT streams, efficiently processed by native MM-AI support, will enable extended awareness of ER crews. Through advanced perception, localisation, navigation, tracking, and decision-making recommendation services, field ER staff will receive real-time updates through XR/AR content, while command ER staff will be provided with back-end visualisation and decision-making support.

Fig. 2. Conceptual Architectural Framework for 6G Intelligent Emergency Response Services.

VI. TECHNICAL GAPS, CHALLENGES AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The vision in Sec. V demands substantial evolution of current 3GPP 5G Advanced system. This section explores the key challenges, identifies gaps, and provides recommendations for advancing this vision.

UAVs, Wearables, and AMRs: Integrating UAV-attached base stations (UAV-BS), enhanced wearable technology, AMRs, and immersive control centers into ER operations faces significant challenges. UAV-BS struggle with limited battery life, signal interference, and regulatory hurdles. Wearable technology integration requires overcoming data processing, latency, and user interface design challenges. Deploying AI-powered AMRs presents navigation complexities, obstacle avoidance, and ethical considerations. Establishing immersive control centers necessitates addressing data visualization, real-time data integration, and user training. Furthermore, ensuring reliable communication between robots and control centers in dynamic environments remains a challenge. A limited understanding of existing robotic systems' capabilities hinders their effective deployment, and building trust in robots operating in unpredictable environments requires robust safety and reliability measures. Finally, fostering trust between rescue workers and AMRs is essential for successful integration.

3D Networking: While UAV-BS and ground stations promise robust 3DN for seamless connectivity in disaster response, several challenges remain. Developing predictive and proactive handovers, and real-time optimization based on diverse UEs and service requirements, pose significant complexities. A lack of seamless and reliable handover mechanisms that consider mobility prediction and real-time channel quality hinders optimal performance. Handover success rate and latency need to be addressed to ensure uninterrupted communication during complex operations.

Seamless 6G Indoor-Outdoor Positioning: While multi-technology positioning systems hold promise for accurate tracking of responders and affected individuals in disaster re-

sponse, several challenges remain. Ensuring reliable positioning in environments with strong electromagnetic interference and addressing power and processing constraints of portable devices are critical. Achieving seamless integration of RF sensing while ensuring accuracy and low latency in real-time sensing applications is essential. Limited 3GPP standardisation of ISAC and the need for robust multi-modal data fusion represent gaps that need to be addressed.

A-IoT Sensors Integration: Integrating A-IoT sensors with advanced sensing capabilities for continuous environmental monitoring in disaster response faces several challenges. Energy management in A-IoT devices relying on limited power sources and interoperability between diverse A-IoT devices and broader network integration are key hurdles. The need for sidelink communication evolution to support complex IoT networks present critical gaps. Integrating diverse data streams from video, audio, biometric, and environmental sensors into a cohesive situational awareness platform poses difficulties, and the potential for data overload makes extracting actionable insights challenging. Processing diverse data types simultaneously due to varying formats and standards poses a challenge for AI models, and limited access to AI tools for smaller emergency response organizations hinders their ability to leverage these technologies.

Operational and deployment challenges: The successful deployment of 6G intelligent ER systems faces several operational and deployment challenges. Rapidly identifying damaged and operational network nodes is crucial for post-disaster recovery, requiring intelligent network management tools with monitoring and commissioning capabilities. Power supply restoration is critical, as even undamaged infrastructure may be non-operational due to outages. Developing easily-deployable and resilient alternative energy sources is essential for BSs and network data centers. Long-service-life UAV-BS for extended coverage are needed to maintain connectivity during the recovery period. Prioritizing and authorizing intelligent ER services to satellite channels is vital for comprehensive

recovery, particularly in areas where terrestrial or low-altitude platforms are unavailable. Clear legal authorization processes and usage procedures are needed to facilitate rapid deployment and access to network services during and after disasters. Balancing the cost of hardware, power consumption, and weight with sensor capabilities is a significant challenge for IoT applications. Developing sensors that can operate under debris or constrained conditions and increasing the availability of cost-effective products in FR2/3 bands will accelerate the development of 6G intelligent ER services.

Recommendations: To effectively integrate advanced technologies into ER operations, several key recommendations are crucial. Developing robust communication protocols and standardized testing methods will ensure reliable and interoperable systems. Rigorous testing and certification processes will guarantee safety and effectiveness. Investing in immersive 3D control centers with VR/AR capabilities will enhance coordination and strategic planning through real-time data visualization. These shared recommendations should be implemented across all specific technology areas, including: **Autonomous Robots:** Develop robust communication protocols for robots in diverse environments and standardize testing and certification methods for ER robots. **3D Networking:** Develop ML-based predictive handover approaches, standardize handover processes across different systems, and explore dynamic spectrum management using cognitive radio technologies. **Seamless 6G Indoor-Outdoor Positioning and ISAC:** Improve GNSS and visual-inertial odometry integration, develop energy-efficient processing systems, accelerate standardization efforts in 3GPP for ISAC. **Sensing, Real-time Analytics and Multi-Modal Analytics:** Develop advanced sidelink communications for low-power IoT operations, create standardized data formats and protocols for multi-modal data integration, provide training and resources to smaller organizations for AI utilization, develop advanced MM-AI models for data fusion, and implement user-friendly interfaces for accessing and interpreting critical information. **Development of Resilient Power Sources:** Prioritize development of easily deployable and resilient alternative power sources for network infrastructure, and long-service-life UAV-BS with extended coverage. The combined effort will ensure reliable power and communication access during and after disaster events.

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